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Africa's Leadership in Global Development Debates: Contribution of the Common African Position to the Post-2015 Development Agenda and Sustainable Development Goals

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ABSTRACT

The adoption of the Common African Position (CAP) by the African Union in 2014 marked a transformative shift in Africa's engagement with global development, shaping the post-2015 development agenda and sustainable development goals (SDGs). Despite its significance, the CAP's contributions remain underacknowledged in mainstream narratives. This study addresses this epistemic gap by examining the CAP's emergence and influence through an elite interview with a key policymaker involved in its formulation and a detailed documentary analysis of AU and UN records. The findings show that via the CAP African countries made an important contribution to the SDG process. Evidence from the interview indicates that African negotiators used the CAP as a shared framework to articulate common priorities and strengthen Africa's collective bargaining position in global negotiations. A documentary analysis was also undertaken to validate these claims, and confirms that the CAP's principles emphasising social inclusion, environmental sustainability and equitable global partnerships influenced the framing and content of several SDG targets. The CAP presented a unified African voice and vision of development, highlighting the interaction between the social, economic and environmental aspects of development for future global agendas. We argue that, as equity, multilateralism and development face challenges, acknowledging African ideas and perspectives becomes crucial to redress epistemic inequalities and to envision alternative solutions for addressing the development challenges of the continent and the world in a context of contested multilateralism.

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Africa continues to be a pawn in the international political chessboard, but Western observers must discard some long-held popular misconceptions about the continent (Helen Kitchen)

1 | Introduction

Africa remains a suitable site for extraction and exploitation, a condition with deep historical roots (Nunn 2008; Mavhunga 2023). The transatlantic slave trade, beginning in 1502, marked a decisive turning point in the global economic order, inaugurating a pattern that positioned Africa as a reservoir of raw materials for Western expansion (Mavhunga 2023). Through the use of firearms and manufactured goods, European powers cultivated alliances with complicit African rulers and entrenched a system of asymmetrical exchange. The legacies of this extractive order persist today in development policy and in the dominant epistemologies that continue to define what counts as 'development' (Olorunfoba and Falola 2022).

The perception of Africa and the rest of the developing world as passive rather than active drivers of development is closely tied to the enduring practises of colonial and neocolonial exploitation. This framing has profoundly shaped development policies and practises, often marginalising African perspectives on needs and priorities (Boisvert 2015; Atela et al. 2017; Cheru 2017). The effects of this exclusion are far from benign, and are seen in the ostracising of African knowledge systems from major development interventions such as the structural adjustment programmes (SAPs) of the 1980s and 1990s and the millennium development goals (MDGs) of the 2000s, and the collateral damage of such exclusion in the lives, and livelihoods of those whose ideas and realities are silenced and ignored.

However, despite the Western colonial gaze on what development should be and whose ideas we account for, Africans have contested these imposed visions and continue to challenge such worldviews to present their voices and perspectives in global development discussions. Africans continue to surface their ideas into national, regional and continental agendas and frameworks that reflect their desires and aspirations. These efforts continue despite persistent ongoing indifference, outright opposition, or even sabotage from existing and emerging global powers.

To illustrate Africans' influence on shaping global agendas, we examined the role of African proposals on global development agendas. More specifically, we examine contributions from the African Union (AU), particularly the 2014 Common African Position, also known as CAP. The CAP on the post-2015 development agenda refers to the collective vision established by African countries about the needs of future global development agendas. Its primary aim was to ensure representation of the continent's needs and ideas in future global development agendas, but also managed to inform and influence the debates on the post-2015 development agenda (AU 2014a) which led to the sustainable development goals (SDGs).

Launched during the 50th anniversary of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), later the AU, the CAP was grounded in Africa's long-term experiences and vision for what global development agendas should consider (AU 2014a). It asserted Africa's collective vision by embedding key priorities such as peace, industrialisation, equity and environmental and social sustainability into the debates that shaped the SDGs (AU 2014a). Its launch coincided with global reflections on the limitations of technocratic, reductionist approaches to development and the growing recognition of the importance of inclusive development frameworks (Mkandawire 2015). The CAP articulated a vision of development rooted in the specific needs and realities of the African context. This positional document challenged the epistemic asymmetries that have marginalised African intellectual contributions in global development scholarship (AU 2014a; Zondi 2017) and helped to inform the conceptualisation of the SDGs (Kamau et al. 2018). However, despite these contributions, the role of the CAP and Africa's input in the post-2015 development agenda and SDG discussions remains largely eclipsed, marginalised, underexplored and under-accounted in mainstream development debates.

Narratives about the emergence of the SDGs are often attributed solely to the Global North, relegating the roles of African and other developing countries to the periphery of knowledge production (Chipaike and Knowledge 2018; Caballero and Londoño 2019). This marginalisation reflects a broader failure within development studies to adequately recognise and address the needs and aspirations of developing countries. Ideas from African countries are often acknowledged only when they are reformulated into a 'Western' framework or subordinated to Western paradigms. The CAP, in contrast, illustrates how African perspectives can enter global development debates on their own terms. At the same time, it is important to recognise that engaging with the language and formats of global development may itself be seen as a form of conformity to dominant frameworks. Nevertheless, the CAP demonstrates a deliberate effort to assert African agency within these structures, seeking to shape debates without merely adopting external agendas. The CAP illustrates the capacity of African ideas to shape, inform and influence broader visions of what development should entail, challenging existing epistemic hierarchies and asserting the legitimacy of African knowledge in global policy discussions.

In accounting for the emergence and the influence of the CAP on the SDGs, this study challenges the epistemicide of African knowledge in development (Mignolo 2007; Santos 2014; Abudu 2022; Zembylas 2025) by addressing three research questions: (1) How did the CAP shape the development of the SDGs? (2) What are the thematic and policy synergies between the AU's CAP and the SDGs? (3) What does the CAP reveal about African agency in the global development debates?

To do this, the study employs a decolonial theoretical framework that foregrounds African epistemic agency and underscores the ways African knowledge and priorities actively shape global agenda-setting processes. It applies the concepts of global epistemic injustice and epistemic decolonisation to account for the epistemicide of African knowledge in development and to analyse how Africa, through the CAP, sought to influence the

post-2015 development agenda and the SDGs in challenging this epistemicide.

This approach is grounded in the understanding of how enduring hierarchies of knowledge continue to position Africa as a passive recipient rather than a source of ideas. It draws on Mignolo's (2007) concept of epistemic disobedience, which refers to the deliberate refusal to accept Western-dominated ways of knowing as universal and the assertion of the validity of diverse knowledge systems, and on Santos's (2014) insight into the persistence of epistemicide in the suppression of non-Western epistemologies, particularly those of the Global South. Our methodological approach resonates with Abudu's (2022) critiques of African development, which highlight how Enlightenment-derived rationalism has long marginalised African knowledge and produced epistemic violence through externally imposed frameworks. It also aligns with Mignolo's (2007) plea for delinking from Western epistemic dominance and for recognising a pluriversal world in which multiple knowledge systems coexist. Extending these insights, and drawing on Zembylas (2025), we understand epistemic freedom as the capacity of societies to interpret and theorise their own realities independently of external validation.

Santos (2014) and Abudu (2022) conceptualise epistemic decolonisation as an intellectual and political project aimed at restoring the authority of the Global South, and particularly Africa, to define, produce and legitimise its knowledge. Within this framework, the CAP functions as an act of epistemic affirmation, bringing African priorities into global development debates and advancing structural transformation, equity and culturally grounded approaches. Its engagement in the discussions that shaped the SDGs demonstrates both the potential of epistemic decolonisation and the limitations imposed by persistent epistemic hierarchies. Africa's participation in global development debates continues to challenge these asymmetries and underscores the importance of recognising diverse forms of knowledge production in shaping future global governance.

This study employs qualitative research methods to examine how African actors contributed to and influenced the global development agenda through the CAP. Empirically, it draws primarily on desk-based research, complemented by an elite interview with an official involved in drafting the CAP, which provides firsthand insights into Africa's negotiating stance and the strategies embedded within the document. The desk review analysed the CAP's drafting process, the presentation of its ideas in global development debates and the discussions surrounding the post-2015 development agenda. It examined official AU and UN documents, as well as scholarly research in development studies and international relations, to trace the CAP's role and impact on the deliberations that culminated in the adoption of the SDGs. The elite interview explored the CAP's normative significance, the challenges of translating its principles into the global development agenda, and the diplomatic processes that shaped both the CAP itself and its influence on post-2015 negotiations.

The findings and discussions are structured into four key areas: the historical context of African marginalisation in

development debates, the CAP's strategic formulation, the synergies between the CAP and the SDGs and the challenges in reasserting African agency in development debates. These findings from this study reveal how African actors actively countered the marginalisation of their knowledge through the CAP and, in doing so, reshaped global development narratives.

2 | Africa's Marginalisation in Development Debates and the Rationale for the CAP

Africa has long been a wellspring of ideas that enrich vision and inform debates concerning the world's past, present and future. Nonetheless, it continues to experience financial, political and economic marginalisation. This marginalisation is not accidental but the outcome of entrenched biases and practises of domination deeply rooted in epistemic injustice and unequal global power dynamics, siblings from the same colonial litter (Santos 2014). Africa's marginalisation extends beyond ideas to the global political economy. As illustrated in a report by the Economic Commission for Africa (ECA), Africa's share of global trade remains less than 3%, primarily as a provider of raw minerals and materials (Karingi 2021). This lack of economic influence limits Africa's capacity to act as a powerful global player and reduces its bargaining power in shaping global development policymaking.

Due to the limited participation and leverage of Africans in global development agenda formulation, the framing, interpretation and direction of Africa's development paths and ideas have been shaped primarily by Western intellectuals, institutions and donor agencies, often at the expense of African scholars, policymakers and knowledge systems (Gani and Marshall 2022). This marginalisation is evident in historical interventions such as the implementation of SAPs, which imposed externally designed economic reforms with minimal input from local actors across the continent during the 1980s and 1990s. These programmes, guided by international financial institutions, produced currency devaluations, inflationary pressures and reductions in public services, resulting in widespread socioeconomic challenges (Nondo and Kumah-Abiwu 2022). Similarly, the drafting of the MDGs in 2000 saw African participation as largely consultative rather than directive, limiting the incorporation of African priorities and perspectives into the global development agenda (Yansane 2005). For many in sub-Saharan Africa, the MDGs were perceived as yet another initiative envisioned and driven by developed countries, with little chance of success (Yansane 2005) as they omitted issues that were critical to the development of many African countries (Easterly 2009). This omission was a byproduct of the deliberate exclusion of ideas from African governments, scholars and civil society (Hulme 2007). These historical examples underscore the enduring legacy of colonial and neocolonial exploitation in shaping development policies that overlook African agency and knowledge systems.

The persistent marginalisation of African agency in global development is evident in how foreign actors, including Western governments, multilateral institutions such as the World Bank and private philanthropies, dominate Africa's infrastructural

development through grants and loans. These actors often prioritise their own strategic interests over African-led goals of sustainable growth and economic sovereignty. For example, the World Bank has mobilised a \$100 billion low-cost loan facility through its International Development Association (IDA), with 70% or \$70 billion allocated to Africa to counter declining global aid and support critical investments in infrastructure, health and education (Tadesse 2025). Such projects often sideline local expertise and community-driven development models, thereby perpetuating a political economy that leads to epistemicide.

This dominance of Western ideas illustrates how the coloniality of knowledge continues to relegate African ideas to secondary or marginal status (Ndlovu 2018). Such practises legitimise the imposition of policies and ideas from developed countries and well-meaning external benefactors onto developing countries. For example, between 2000 and 2015, the period of the implementation of the MDGs, African countries were primarily treated as implementers of externally designed goals rather than co-creators, resulting in interventions disconnected from local realities, leading to weakened industries, debilitated public service provision and the hindering of the development of local policies and governance structures (Fentahun 2023).

Vandemoortele (2011) also critiques the disconnect between global ambitions and local realities and needs, which often ostracises local knowledge under the guise of technocratic approaches and their inherent blind spots. A key example is the implementation of health programmes that sidelined community-based systems. These initiatives, driven by global institutions and donor agencies, prioritised standardised interventions such as vaccination campaigns and hospital-based care over local health networks, infrastructure needs and traditional practises. Rooted in the MDGs' reliance on universal benchmarks, this approach overlooked contextual nuances, including the critical role of community health workers in sub-Saharan Africa. The MDGs' 'one-size-fits-all' mentality and donor-driven agendas marginalised local priorities, underfunded systemic issues such as primary healthcare, and concentrated decision-making among global elites, thereby reducing local ownership and accountability. Consequently, health strategies were often unattainable. A recent manifestation of this marginalisation was evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, when global health policies largely ignored Africa's experience in managing epidemics such as Ebola, particularly in relation to vaccine manufacturing. This neglect undermined the effectiveness of global initiatives and prolonged the pandemic's impact in the region.

Global organisations such as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) are not immune to the global political economy of development and the coloniality of knowledge. Despite their stated aspirations for equitable development, these organisations have contributed to sustaining systemic biases against the voices and agency of developing countries (Skosireva and Holaday 2010). In African development, these entities often apply a 'one-size-fits-all' approach in policy formulation. They favour models aligned with Western economic systems, ways of working and interests grounded in

Western worldviews. These models maintain aid dependency rather than promoting trade, manufacturing, or investment. They also fail to respond to African development objectives, governmental frameworks, or local needs (Emeagwali 2011). Despite critiques, power asymmetries have allowed international organisations to continue to impose external conditions that prioritise donor countries' worldviews over African livelihoods and development (Emeagwali 2011).

Why is this happening? This situation occurs because African countries' agency is systematically misrepresented. Policymakers and governmental institutions are often treated as implementers rather than owners of their development agendas. This misrepresentation positions African countries as subjects expected to follow external directives from actors who claim to 'understand' what is good for them. The portrayal of Africa in global debates is often constrained between stereotypical Western perceptions and the depiction by well-meaning actors who see Africa primarily as a recipient of aid. This framing obscures Africa's capacity to act as a continent with agency and to shape its own development.

The absence of African representation in key global organisations, multilateral institutions, global debates and other international forums reflects deeper systemic issues that perpetuate the marginalisation of African countries in global decision-making. The lack of permanent African seats at the UN Security Council (UNSC) and the limited voting power of African countries in Bretton Woods institutions illustrate how global decision-making bodies fail to accommodate the voices and interests of developing nations (Murithi 2023), limiting Africa's ability to shape policies that directly affect its populations (Machrouh 2024).

The persistent relegation of African countries to secondary or tertiary status in international discussions cannot be overlooked. Even when African perspectives are included, their contributions are often interpreted through a Western-centric lens. African countries are seen as following and supporting rather than leading. The appearance of inclusivity is frequently used to suggest that global institutions are representative or democratic. This tokenism undermines genuine engagement and reduces African contributions to footnotes, statistics, or case studies that primarily serve the interests of global powers.

It is important to note that this discussion does not aim to portray Africa as a victim. Rather, it highlights how African countries continue to assert their presence in global development debates despite structural disadvantages and limited representation. This persistence demonstrates remarkable agency. The drafting of the CAP (AU 2014a) exemplifies this collective effort to bring African voices, ideas and experiences into global development deliberations.

3 | The Emergence of the CAP and Its Influence Within Global Development Thinking

To introduce the CAP on the post-2015 development agenda, this section outlines the framework, its key elements,

the principal actors involved in its formulation, the timeline of its development, and the critical components and significance of the CAP within the broader post-2015 development debates.

The adoption of the CAP reflects Africa's response to the limitations of externally imposed development frameworks such as the MDGs. The MDGs envisioned that those who needed to 'develop' were countries outside the West, which perpetuated asymmetrical global development discourses. Although the MDG period introduced broader indicators such as the Human Development Index, this expansion of metrics did not translate into the recognition of perspectives from developing regions in the design or implementation of global agendas (Betteli 2021). The MDGs' one-size-fits-all approach failed to consider diverse historical and institutional contexts. As a result, it produced blind spots and 'statistical distortions' that masked Africa's structural challenges (Mkandawire 2011).

As the MDG period drew to a close, reflections on a successor framework gathered momentum. In 2013, the United Nations encouraged a more democratic form of multilateralism that opened space for inclusivity and dialogue with developing countries in shaping the post-2015 development agenda (Kamau et al. 2018). The process was guided by the principle of universality and by the commitment to 'leave no one behind'. This environment provided a crucial opportunity for Africa to advance its own perspectives and priorities in global development debates (United Nations 2015; Wahutu 2024).

The CAP emerged during a moment of political introspection and renewal within Africa. The 50th anniversary of the OAU in 2013 prompted reflection on the continent's developmental trajectory and its marginal position in global policy dialogues (AU 2014b; Lopes 2023). These discussions encouraged the AU to craft a unified continental response to the evolving global development architecture. The result was the CAP on the post-2015 development agenda, which articulated Africa's priorities, challenges and aspirations for the framework that would succeed the MDGs. The CAP also informed the development of agenda 2063, a long-term continental vision for transformation and integration (Gebrihet et al. 2025).

The CAP's formulation followed a participatory and consensus-based process coordinated by the African Union Commission (AUC) in collaboration with the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) and the African Development Bank (AfDB). Between 2012 and 2014, consultations were held at national, regional and continental levels, engaging governments, Regional Economic Communities (RECs), civil society organisations, women and youth groups, traditional authorities, grassroots activists and academic institutions (AU 2014a). In May 2013, the AU established a High-Level Committee (HLC) of 10 Heads of State and Government, chaired by Liberia's President Ellen Johnson Sirleaf, to provide political leadership and continental coordination. The committee represented all five AU regions and ensured that the CAP reflected Africa's diversity and legitimacy through broad consultation (AU 2014b). Technical support was provided by NEPAD, the AfDB, UNECA, UNDP and UNFPA, which helped strengthen the analytical foundation of the framework.

The origins of the CAP can be traced to the Rio + 20 Conference in June 2012, when the United Nations launched the process to develop a successor framework to the MDGs. One month later, the AU Assembly mandated the AUC to define Africa's post-2015 priorities, formally initiating the CAP process. Between 2012 and early 2014, the AU conducted extensive consultations that culminated in the CAP's formal endorsement on 31 January 2014 in Addis Ababa and its public launch on 28 February 2014 in Ndjamena, Chad. This proactive sequence allowed Africa to present a coherent position before the United Nations Open Working Group (OWG) submitted its proposal for the SDGs in July 2014. As a result, African priorities were incorporated into the global framework that was adopted in September 2015 as the SDGs.

The timeline in Table 1 summarises the major milestones in the development of the CAP and the SDGs, highlighting Africa's strategic engagement in shaping the post-2015 global development agenda.

The CAP influenced the SDGs, making the global agenda more inclusive and relevant to African realities, including economic challenges, social inequalities and sustainability. The CAP identifies six pillars essential for Africa's transformation: structural economic transformation and inclusive growth, science, technology and innovation (STI), people-centred development, environmental sustainability and resource management, peace and security and finance and partnerships. Each of the six pillars respond to the awareness and the challenges faced by African countries (AU 2014a). We proceed to describe briefly the different pillars and their rationale within the CAP.

1. Structural economic transformation and inclusive growth: The CAP acknowledges that structural economic transformation is necessary to build resilient economies, create decent jobs, minimise wealth disparities and ultimately eradicate poverty, counteracting the current trend where resource benefits are concentrated in limited sectors. The position motivates for a commitment to sustained, inclusive economic growth that accelerates diversification, strengthens resilience against external shocks and fosters rapid socioeconomic development through job creation and sustainable social protection.
2. Science, technology and innovation: STI are crucial for Africa's transformative agenda, as the continent is mindful of its low levels of technology transfer and utilisation, coupled with existing capacity deficits. The CAP aim to enhance technological capacities and creating an enabling financial and regulatory environment that supports innovation, research and development (R&D) and the utilisation of environmentally sound technologies and expertise.
3. People-centred development: The AU surfaced the importance of a people-centred development. As the high levels of poverty and inequality in Africa illustrate, sustainable and equitable development is only possible when people, can benefit from economic growth. Commitment under this pillar involves empowering people through inclusive growth and social protection, while responding to

TABLE 1 | Timeline of key milestones in the development of the CAP and the SDGs.

Date	Agenda/ initiative	Event/meeting	Key developments	Reference/participants
June 2012	SDG	Rio + 20 conference kick-off	The United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (SD) (Rio + 20) adopts 'The Future We Want', launching the process to develop successors to the MDGs and establishing the UN High-level Political Forum on SD.	Hosted in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; involved 193 UN member states, governments, NGOs, private sector and civil society; built on 1992 Earth Summit's Agenda 21.
July 2012	CAP	Formal initiation	The AU Summit mandates the AUC to identify Africa's post-2015 priorities in consultation with member states and RECs, responding to global UN processes like Rio + 20.	African Union Assembly (decision: Assembly/AU/Dec. 423 (XIX)); builds on MDGs and NEPAD (2001).
January 2013	SDG	OWG established	The UN General Assembly creates a 30-member OWG to identify and propose specific goals and targets for the SDGs.	UN General Assembly; OWG included representatives from diverse countries; aimed to build on Rio + 20 outcomes.
May 2013	CAP	Establishment of High-Level Committee (HLC)	AU Summit creates the HLC of 10 Heads of State to lead coordination, sensitisation and international alliances.	Chaired by Liberia's President Ellen Johnson Sirleaf; members from Algeria, Chad, Congo, Ethiopia, Guinea, Mauritania, Mauritius, Namibia and South Africa.
2012–2014	CAP	Consultation phase	Multi-level participatory consultations at national, regional and continental scales, gathering inputs from diverse stakeholders.	Governments, private sector, parliamentarians, CSOs, women/youth groups, trade unions and academia; technical support from NEPAD Agency, AfDB, UNECA, UNDP and UNFPA.
2013–2014	SDG	Consultation and proposal phase	Extensive participatory consultations and negotiations through the OWG, incorporating inputs from stakeholders worldwide to draft the SDGs.	UN system, including UNDP; involved governments, civil society and experts.
31 January 2014	CAP	Adoption	CAP finalised and adopted by AU Heads of State during the 22nd Ordinary Session in Addis Ababa.	AU assembly; preamble commits to 'speaking with one voice' across aa member states.
March 2014	CAP	Official publication	The CAP is published by the AU.	AUC, under Chairperson Dr. Nkosazana Dlamini Zuma.
3 June 2014	CAP	Public launch	CAP launched in Addis Ababa to engage the UN OWG and international community.	AU, HLC; influenced SDGs.
July 2014	SDG	OWG proposal finalised	The OWG submits its proposal for 17 SDGs and 169 targets to the UN General Assembly, setting the foundation for the final agenda.	OWG was proposal influenced by CAP (adopted earlier in January 2014).
January 2015	SDG	Negotiation process begins	The UN General Assembly starts formal negotiations on the post-2015 development agenda, refining the OWG proposal.	UN General Assembly; involved member states and stakeholders.
September 2015	SDG	Adoption of the 2030 agenda	UN member states adopt the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the 17 SDGs, at the UN Sustainable Development Summit in New York.	UN headquarters; 193 member states.

Source: Compiled from AU (2014a, 2014b) and United Nations (2015).

demographic shifts like the increase in the youth in the continent, by prioritising universal access to quality education and affordable healthcare.

4. Environmental sustainability, natural resources management and disaster risk management: As Africa is the most vulnerable continent to climate change shocks, and climate breakdown, this pillar from the CAP raises the importance to address the potential adverse effects of climate change, desertification and natural disasters, while committing to enhancing access to safe water and strengthening resilience against natural disasters.
5. Peace and security: Peace and security are necessary conditions for achieving any of Africa's development aspirations. Any development agenda must thus tackle with the root causes of conflict, such as social exclusion and economic inequality, and prevent outbreaks of armed conflict by strengthening good and inclusive governance and implementing comprehensive post-conflict reconstruction programmes.
6. Finance and partnerships: Development takes resources, thus financing the CAP requires robust resource mobilisation, emphasising the critical role of improving domestic resource mobilisation, fighting corruption and maximising innovative financing mechanisms that are development enablers.

The CAP's emergence also demonstrated Africa's growing confidence in challenging externally imposed frameworks and narratives. Lopes and Kararach (2019) observe that Western development discourses have often misrepresented African realities and promoted policy prescriptions lacking contextual relevance. The CAP countered this pattern by articulating an African-led vision rooted in consensus, contextual understanding and political resolve. Its integration into broader frameworks such as Agenda 2063 enabled Africa to assert itself as a

legitimate contributor to global development policy and to promote the radical inclusion of developing countries (AU 2014a).

Beyond its immediate influence on the SDGs, the CAP symbolised a broader transformation in Africa's epistemic and political posture. It provided an African perspective for understanding and achieving structural transformation. Drafted by Africans and informed by African experiences, the CAP was designed to challenge entrenched hierarchies of knowledge in global development governance (Kararach et al. 2015). It therefore stands as a milestone in Africa's ongoing effort to redefine development discourse and to move from the position of a passive recipient to that of an active and confident shaper of global development ideas.

4 | Thematic and Policy Synergies Between the CAP and the SDGs

The synergies between the CAP and the SDGs are multiple and stem from the AU's strategic decision to table the CAP prior to several regional initiatives and gatherings associated with African contributions to post-2015 development agenda discussions (see Table 1). This timing allowed the CAP to inform and shape global development ideas that ultimately contributed to the SDGs (AU 2014b). The influence of the CAP is evident in the alignment between its pillars and the goals articulated in the SDGs, which reflects the central themes envisioned for future development agendas. To illustrate this contribution, we highlight the resonance of the different CAP pillars with the corresponding SDG goals.

The CAP was structured around six interlinked pillars: structural economic transformation and inclusive growth, STI, people-centred development, environmental sustainability, peace and security and finance and partnerships. These pillars were goals and concerns of African countries in relation to what should be included in a future development agenda. These pillars, as illustrated in Figure 1, resonate with the goals espoused

FIGURE 1 | Synergies between the CAP and the SDGs. Source: Authors' illustration based on CAP and SDG frameworks.

by the SDGs, illustrating how CAP ideas became central to the ideas of the SDGs (AU 2014a).

Priorities such as employment, agricultural production, value addition in supply chains, agro-industry development, trade, infrastructure and regional integration are central to the ideas of the CAP on structural transformation and influenced the discussions on several of the goals of the SDGs, including SDG 1 (no poverty), SDG 2 (zero hunger), SDG 8 (decent work and economic growth), SDG 9 (industry, innovation and infrastructure) and SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production) (AU 2014a, 2014b).

Central to this vision, the CAP's STI pillar championed African-led solutions to drive sustainable development, aligning with SDG 9 by promoting technological innovation and industrial growth, SDG 3 (good health and well-being) through mobile health technologies such as telemedicine, and SDG 4 (quality education) via digital learning platforms that expand access to education (AU 2014a). Similarly, the CAP's emphasis on people-centred development resonated with SDG 1, SDG 2, SDG 3, SDG 5 (gender equality), SDG 4 and SDG 10 (reduced inequalities), prioritising youth empowerment, social protection and equitable education to foster inclusive growth (AU 2014b; Kamau et al. 2018).

The CAP's environmental priorities, climate-resilient development, sustainable natural resource management, green growth and biodiversity conservation, resonated in what later emerged as SDG 6 (clean water and sanitation), SDG 7 (affordable and clean energy), SDG 11 (sustainable cities and communities), SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production), SDG 13 (climate action), SDG 14 (life below water) and SDG 15 (life on land) (AU 2014a).

A significant contribution towards the SDGs was the CAP's integration of peace and security into global development frameworks. Historically, peace and security have been sidelined from development discussions, as illustrated by how the MDGs sidelined peace and security altogether (Hickmann et al. 2023). By explicitly framing peace as a prerequisite for sustainable development in Africa, the CAP helped frame SDG 16 (peace, justice and strong institutions). This principle was actively championed by prominent African Nobel Peace Prize laureates, such as Ellen Johnson Sirleaf, whose efforts alongside UNECA's advocacy helped elevate post-conflict recovery and institutional reform as central priorities within international development discourse. Through their participation in influential forums, such as the UN high-level panel on the post-2015 development agenda and the CAP champion group, they played a critical role in articulating and promoting the CAP at the global level.

The emphasis on equitable partnerships, as advocated by the CAP, highlighted the necessity of addressing the imbalances present in global collaborations. This initiative promoted equitable cooperation grounded in mutual respect, fair trade and shared accountability, thereby influencing the discourse that culminated in the establishment of SDG 17 (AU 2014a).

CAP ideas and concerns not only relate to the goals sought by the post 2015 development agenda but also emerged in the implementation and monitoring frameworks envisioned

by the SDGs. One of the main challenges in understanding pathways for development is the MDGs' reliance on aggregate quantitative indicators that are mostly deaf to contextual factors. African negotiators, supported by both the UNECA and UNDP, advocated for disaggregated, qualitative and context-specific metrics to capture the nuances of the contexts in which development was to take place (AU 2014a; Lopes 9/2023, interview). These efforts led to more inclusive evaluation mechanisms in the SDG framework, ensuring that diverse developmental realities were recognised (Kamau et al. 2018). This shift, rooted in the CAP's critique of universalism, enhanced the responsiveness and accountability of global monitoring systems.

Through the CAP's concerns and suggestions, Africa transcended its role as a policy recipient to become a contributor, proponent and strategic actor that contributed ideas central to the SDGs in which Africa could offer a model for global leadership in multilateralism (Kararach et al. 2015). This integrative ethos positioned and inscribed the continent's ideas on global development, contributing to a more inclusive and realistic conceptualisation of global development (United Nations 2015). The CAP helped in catalysing a conceptual shift from the fragmented, sectoral approach of the MDGs to an integrated and holistic architecture that saw development as a dynamic interplay of economic, social and environmental dimensions, as captured by the SDGs (AU 2014a).

Table 2 presents a thematic mapping approach that builds on Figure 1 by highlighting textual overlaps, shared priorities and conceptual alignments between the CAP and SDGs. The synergies between the Continental Agenda Position (CAP) and the SDGs are presented below by mapping the CAP's pillars to the SDG targets. As illustrated by Table 2, for each pillar of the CAP we summarise the synergies between the pillars and the SDG goals, surfacing the similarities in the wording between the CAP pillars (which preceded the SDGs) but also, how the commitments of the CAP relate and resonate in the final proposals by the SDGs across different indicators.

5 | Reasserting African Agency: Challenging Epistemicide in Global Development Debates

The CAP marked a shift in Africa's global engagement. While Africa had been characterised as having a 'mediocre African agency' that had constrained the continent's influence in the past (Lopes 9/2023, interview), the CAP illustrates that Africa can choose to exert its agency and advance its ideas on the global stage. It challenged longstanding epistemic inequalities in development, where Western institutions often marginalised African perspectives and their own concerns and insights about development. It confronted these asymmetries by leveraging the continent's intellectual agency (AU 2014a; Wahutu 2024).

Central to the CAP's objectives on the post-2015 development agenda was its articulation of African development ideas. This proposal was not merely a proposal for the global consideration of principles and suggestions, but rather as a fully realised and homegrown agenda in the form of Agenda 2063 (Gebrihet 2025).

TABLE 2 | Synergies between the CAP and the SDGs.

CAP pillars	CAP wording	SDG	SDG wording
1. Structural economic transformation and inclusive growth	‘Accelerated, stable and sustained inclusive economic growth that creates decent and productive employment that reduces inequality’	SDG 8/ Target 8.5	‘By 2030, achieve full and productive employment and decent work for all... and equal pay for work of equal value’
	‘Enhance the production... quality of food... Improve the productivity of smallholder agriculture... Promote agricultural marketing’	SDG 2/ Target 2.3	‘By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers... including through equal access to land’
	‘Develop... reliable, sustainable... affordable infrastructure... with a focus on land, water and air transport... energy... ICT’	SDG 9/ Target 9.1	‘Develop quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure... to support economic development... with a focus on affordable and equitable access for all’
2. Science, technology and innovation	‘Enhancing the development, transfer and diffusion of technology and innovation... strengthening the science and technology component of education curricula’	SDG 9/ Target 9.5	‘Enhance scientific research, upgrade the technological capabilities... encouraging innovation and substantially increasing... research and development’
	‘Strengthening the financial and regulatory environment to support an innovation culture... increasing funding for science and technology research’ (para. 30)	SDG 17/ Target 17.8	‘Fully operationalise the technology bank and science, technology and innovation capacity-building mechanism... and enhance the use of enabling technology’
3. People-centred development	‘Eradication of poverty in all its forms... empowerment of all people... inclusive growth that creates decent jobs’	SDG 1/ Target 1.2	‘By 2030, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions’
	‘Achieve excellence in human resources capacity development... improvement in the quality of education and training... increasing the use of ICT’	SDG 4/ Target 4.4	‘By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills’
	‘Improve the health status... reduce the incidence of communicable diseases... ensure universal and equitable access to quality healthcare’	SDG 3/ Target 3.8	‘Achieve universal health coverage... access to quality essential healthcare services and access to safe, effective... vaccines for all’
	‘Enhancing women’s occupational mobility... ensuring their access to... land and other productive assets... eradicating all forms of violence’	SDG 5/ Target 5.1	‘End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere’
4. Environmental sustainability, natural resources management and disaster risk management	‘Promoting sustainable utilisation of the continent’s natural resources and biodiversity... ensuring that the use... will financially and economically benefit’	SDG 12/ Target 12.2	‘By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources’
	‘Ensure universal and reliable access to safe water... enhancing the protection of water resources... improving wastewater and water quality management’	SDG 6/ Target 6.1	‘By 2030, achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all’
	‘Reduce deforestation, desertification... improve land management... implement the Kyoto Protocol’	SDG 13/ Target 13.1	‘Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries’
5. Peace and security	‘Tackle economic and social inequalities and exclusion; strengthen good governance; fight against all forms of discrimination’	SDG 16/ Target 16.7	‘Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision making at all levels’
	‘Prevent the outbreak of armed conflicts... implementing comprehensive, post-conflict reconstruction programmes’	SDG 16/ Target 16.1	‘Significantly reduce all forms of violence and related death rates everywhere’

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

CAP pillars	CAP wording	SDG	SDG wording
6. Finance and partnerships	‘Improve domestic resource mobilisation... ensuring financial deepening... curtailing illicit financial flows and fight corruption’	SDG 17/ Target 17.1	‘Strengthen domestic resource mobilisation... to improve domestic capacity for tax... collection’
	‘Enhancing the quality and predictability of external financing... holding external partners accountable for their commitments’	SDG 17/ Target 17.2	‘Developed countries to implement fully their official development assistance commitments’
	‘Accelerate regional integration including by boosting intra-African trade... promoting Africa’s access to global markets and the fair-trade system’	SDG 17/ Target 17.10	‘Promote a universal, rules-based, open, non-discriminatory and equitable multilateral trading system under the World Trade Organisation’

Source: Compiled from AU (2014a) and United Nations (2015).

This alignment of a continental position with a comprehensive development framework allowed African actors to engage more assertively in shaping global development discourse. As Lopes (9/2023, interview) observes, the combination of the CAP’s shared vision with the concrete roadmap provided by Agenda 2063 enabled Africa to influence the formulation of the SDGs, particularly by highlighting the interdependence of social, political and environmental sustainability, demonstrating Africa’s potential to shape norms, and hopefully aligning action towards development (Tieku 2019).

The 2014 CAP on the post-2015 development agenda remains a diplomatic milestone, uniting a historically divided continent to speak with one voice during the negotiations that led to the SDGs (AU 2014a; Lopes 9/2023, interview). The CAP should not be seen as an exception, but rather as an example of how commitment and coordination between AU members increases Africa’s negotiating power (Kamau et al. 2018).

While the CAP on the post-2015 development agenda was successful in influencing the SDGs, the exercise of undertaking collective action in national development plans across Africa remains a challenge. Structural, political and economic constraints have limited the practical impact of CAP’s influence on the SDGs to bring about development or better development programmes in Africa. The tension lies in implementation at the national level, even though consensus was reached on the CAP. Divergent interests among the 54 member states have resulted in competing national priorities that often clash with continental commitments. These tensions, compounded by weak institutional capacities, undermine the implementation of the CAP’s principles as well as the broader goals of Agenda 2063 (Lopes 9/2023, interview). These hurdles underscore the complexity of development beyond dominant narratives and highlight the persistent challenges Africa faces in implementing development and good governance initiatives (Gebrihet and Eidsvik 2024; Gebrihet and Gebresilassie 2024).

Countries on the continent still need to walk their talk. These challenges remain associated with the tension between self-sufficiency and CAP’s vision. While advocating for autonomous development, Africa continues to depend on international financing for its development, including critical areas such as infrastructure, education and scientific research (AU 2014a), perhaps no better illustrated than the human

toll after the USA decided to cut USAID funds. The case of the USA and the use of intimidation as a tool for negotiation waged by the Trump government highlights how pressure from donors and funding institutions can take more or less crass shapes, but illustrates how the vision of what and how development should be achieved, which often diverges from local realities, visions and initiatives and leads to development being conditioned by the interests and visions of other actors (Zondi 2017).

Other critiques highlight the CAP’s outward-facing orientation, arguing that its alignment with global frameworks has led to the sidelining of grassroots organisations, concerns and initiatives, such as rural livelihoods, informal economies and community interests (Cheru 2017). According to this critique, the CAP is a well-meaning idea of what development should be but crafted mostly by African elites and disregarding the value and knowledge of grassroots organisations. This critique reflects the broader dilemma of balancing global engagement and discourse with local priorities and practises. While the CAP’s global influence was a diplomatic triumph, its human legacy remains bound not by diplomacy but by its practise, the capacity to adjust and respond to local realities to ensure inclusive development beyond narratives (Kararach et al. 2015).

The limitations of the CAP on the post 2015 development agenda and its practise reflect the structural challenges of development, but not necessarily a failure of its vision. The tension between narratives and realities, weak institutional capacities and funding constraints continue to hinder the implementation of the CAP’s vision and goals of Agenda 2063, underscoring the need for sustained investment in good governance and institutions (Tieku 2019; Lopes 9/2023, interview; Gebrihet and Eidsvik 2024). As a milestone of the African agencies, the 2014 CAP on the post 2015 development agenda laid critical groundwork for the future, but it was not the destination by itself. Development continues as a process. Therefore, its relevance hinges on translating its vision into tangible outcomes, closing the gap between aspiration and action for Africans in a multipolar world.

6 | Conclusion and Policy Implications

The CAP on the post-2015 development agenda reflects how Africa’s agency can be part of global engagements and

discussions, making equal participation and debate more than an aspiration to fulfil a right to a reality. By bringing the voice of 54 nations under a shared vision, leveraging their ideas and initiatives with well-backed proposals, the CAP on the post-2015 development agenda informed and influenced the discussions of the SDGs and what equitable and sustainable development should be.

The influence of CAP's ideas on the SDGs and development frameworks was facilitated by the inclusive process undertaken by the UN and facilitated by the UN. In this case, the UN fulfilled its mission as a forum for dialogue. The fulfilment of this mandate allowed African countries to present their ideas and contribute to the debate on what principles should inform a new development agenda, the CAP pillars. Grounded in the long-term vision of Africa's development agenda, Agenda 2063, the CAP asserted the capacity and value of African ideas and positioned its ideas and epistemes as a valid vision of development.

Nevertheless, CAP's vision has faced significant hurdles. The challenge of self-sufficiency clashed with dependence on external funding for critical sectors, such as health, infrastructure and education, raising questions about genuine autonomy in a global system marked by structural imbalances. Some critics highlight that CAP's global orientation has occasionally overshadowed grassroots priorities such as rural livelihoods and informal economies, underscoring the challenge of balancing international influence with local relevance. These challenges are compounded by the limitations of governance and institutional capacities of African countries. Africa continues to face the problem of a lack of statehood, which blocks the possibility of sovereignty and development.

These challenges do not diminish the transformative potential of CAP in challenging epistemic inequities. By cultivating a unified voice, the CAP showcased Africa's intellectual contributions, insights and knowledge of global debates.

Looking forward, the CAP lays a critical groundwork. CAP's influence set a precedent for collective advocacy, offering lessons for navigating diversity and inequality in a multilateral setting. However, to realise its potential, the continent must strengthen institutional capacities, reduce dependence on external financing and ensure that global aspirations and continental aspirations align with local realities, which demand governance and solid policymaking.

7 | Scope, Limitations and Future Research Directions

This study examines the development of the CAP between 2013 and 2014 and its influence on the adoption of the SDGs in 2015, with a particular focus on Africa's leadership in shaping the global development agenda during this period. While this scope captures the CAP's formative influence, it does not extend to the subsequent phases of SDG implementation across African countries. The post-2015 period presents important empirical terrain for assessing how the CAP's principles, priorities and epistemic assertions have been translated into policy frameworks and development practises.

Future research should therefore explore the implementation gaps between the CAP's normative vision and the realities of SDG execution at national and regional levels. Such studies could investigate how structural constraints, political economy dynamics and continued epistemic inequalities affect the localisation of global goals in African contexts. Comparative analyses across countries would be valuable for understanding variations in how the CAP's agenda has been institutionalised and whether its call for policy space and knowledge sovereignty has materialised in practise.

Methodologically, while this study drew on official documents and an elite interview to illuminate the CAP's formulation process, these sources may underrepresent grassroots and subnational perspectives. Future research should therefore integrate participatory and community-level approaches to capture how local actors interpret and enact the CAP's development principles. Despite these limitations, the qualitative approach adopted here provides a strong conceptual foundation for re-theorising African agency in global development governance and for advancing a research agenda that critically examines how Africa continues to negotiate epistemic and policy spaces within evolving global frameworks.

Author Contributions

The first author conceived the study, collected and analysed the data, drafted the primary manuscript and interpreted the results. The second author assisted with the manuscript review and writing and contributed to the interpretation of the results. The third author contributed to data collection and manuscript review.

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Ethics Statement

The study involved interviews with Carlos Lopes, then the Executive Secretary of the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA). Informed consent was obtained from all the participants prior to the interviews. Ethical clearance from the institutional review board was not sought, as the study involved a single interview with a public figure and did not involve vulnerable populations or sensitive personal data.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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